

Resilient and fragile social housing systems: The micro political economy of social renting in Western Europe

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1. Introduction

Housing is often described as “the wobbly pillar under the welfare state” (Torgersen, 1987) because many scholars think that housing plays a modest role in welfare states and is more prone to retrenchment than other welfare services and social security benefits. Kemeny (1995) points out that substantial nonmarket decommodified housing provision – in the form of social rented housing - has emerged only in a select group of advanced countries, primarily in Western Europe and to a lesser extent in the Anglophone countries outside Europe and the advanced economies in East Asia. Harloe (1995) agrees that housing has remained the ‘the least decommodified, most market determined’ sector of the welfare state because, even in those countries, where social housing is provided, it has remained a minority and very fragile tenure in every free-market economy. In his view large scale social housing is an ‘abnormal’ form of provision, which only emerges as part of an effort to resolve a systemic social and economic crisis and, when this crisis is resolved, the sector tends to shrink and revert to what he considers the more normal, small and targeted model of provision. Lundqvist echoes this view He argues that large scale social housing provision became too expensive for governments by the 1990s and government intervention in housing provision shifted from ‘the comprehensive and general to the supplementary and specific’ (Lundqvist, 1992). Pierson’s (1994) study of neo-liberal inspired attempts at Dismantling the Welfare State in the UK and USA during the 1980s concludes that these were largely unsuccessful with the notable exception of social housing, which he suggests is far more vulnerable to retrenchment than other welfare programmes.

This pessimistic view of the resilience of social housing sectors reflects the evidence regarding the direction of policy change in recent decades, particularly in the Anglophone world and in most former communist countries of Central and Eastern Europe. A sizeable literature has accumulated which indicates that social housing has borne the brunt of public spending cuts introduced since the late 1970s in Australia, Canada, England, Ireland and the United States and, as a result, it has contracted and also residualised (i.e. become increasingly focused on housing the poorest and most socially excluded households) (Scanlon, Whitehead & Arrigoitia, 2014; Byrne & Norris, 2018; Pawson, 2006; Dalton, 2009; Vale & Freemark, 2012). Following the fall of communism in the late 1990s/ early 2000s the state-owned housing which had been provided under this system in Central and Eastern Europe was privatised in many countries by means of sales to tenants or sometimes given away free of charge. Although this tenure was not entirely equivalent to social housing in the West (because it was not always allocated according to need), the two sectors shared much in common (both are non-market tenures, subsidised by government) (Hegedus & Tosics, 1996). Therefore, this development could be interpreted as further evidence of the fragility of the social housing tenure (Lux & Sunega, 2014).

The literature offers a wide variety of explanations for the particular fragility of social housing compared to the other elements of the welfare state. Harloe's explanation emphasises housing's asset value - because private property rights are central to the operation of market economies, proposals that threaten such rights are more strongly resisted than efforts to decommodify provision of other less economically important and lucrative services such as health. In his view, this explains why large-scale social housing sectors only emerge when limitations on provision of housing by the market are of "strategic importance for the maintenance and development of the capitalist social and economic system" (Harloe, 1995). He suggests that these conditions existed during the Fordist period which followed World War II in some Western European countries, so large social housing sectors emerged at this time but, since the rise of post-Fordism in the 1970s, the social housing sector contracted, and home ownership has come to dominate. Pierson (1994) identifies the 'lumpy' and capital focused nature of government investment in social housing, which is characterised by large one-off investments whose effects are spread over a long period of time, as factors which render this sector uniquely vulnerable to retrenchment. This means that a government can enjoy the benefits of selling social housing to tenants or cutting capital funding for the sector, while the disbenefits in terms of lack of affordable housing supply will be felt by future governments and future generations. The 'tenure modernisation' thesis proposed by Malpass and Murie (1987) and refined by Malpass and Victory (2010) proffers a more directly, functionalist explanation for rise and fall of social housing in the UK. They argue that in the UK social housing provision played a key role in transforming the housing market and underpinning economic and social progress during the mid-twentieth century by providing good quality, and affordable homes to the skilled working class who were both economically and politically powerful during this period. However, the expansion in home ownership drew more middle and lower-income household into this sector while the concurrent contraction of the private rented sector reduced the availability of this housing option. Both of these factors increased the political pressure to target social housing on low-income households only. More recent research points to the role of neo-liberal ideology in justifying reductions in public spending on social housing and privatisation of the sector (e.g. (Rolnik, 2013; Blessing, 2016). However, these studies echo functionalist analyses as far as they also emphasise the practical function of these policy changes in the wider neo-liberalisation project. This commentary has focussed on the role which falling social housing provision has played in forcing more households to look to the private sector for housing and thereby supporting the growth of housing markets and also financial markets which proponents of neo liberalisation believe are the most efficient and effective mode of service delivery and funding (McCabe, 2011; Meek, 2014).

This paper adopts a different approach to these dominant narratives in the literature on social housing. Firstly, it departs from the declinist interpretations of this tenure's trajectory which dominate the literature on social housing. While there is no doubt that this sector has contracted in many developed countries since the late 1970s, more detailed analysis reveals that significant pockets of resilience remain amid this fragility. Most notably, in terms of the proportion of households accommodated in social housing, tenure is static or growing in several of the Western European countries where it has traditionally been strong. Similarly, new output remains high, while outside Europe reliance is also evident in the pockets of social housing provision which exist in the advanced economies of East Asia such as Hong Kong (Ronald & Doling, 2014). Thus, instead of focusing solely on the *fragility of social housing systems* this paper focuses instead on these significant vestiges of *resilience* that have persisted in this tenure and tries to clarify why it has proved resilient in some countries, but fragile in others.

Secondly, although the analysis presented here acknowledges that macro political economy factors, such as the role of social housing in resolving social and economic crises, its function in the housing market and economy and the related issue of the strength or weakness of the political and ideological support it receives play a critical role in shaping the resilience and fragility of the tenure in different countries, these ‘big picture’ factors are not the focus of this paper. In contrast to the norm in the literature, rather than concentrating on the macro level and on the role which political and economic factors primarily external to the social housing system play in shaping its resilience and fragility, this paper focuses on the micro level and on the influence of political and economic factors which are primarily internal to the social housing system. As its title explains, this paper examines the micro-political economy of social housing.

The remainder of the paper is organised into three further sections. The next section outlines the concepts which underpin the analysis and how the countries examined were selected. The main body of the paper then focus on four key micro political economy factors which have exerted the resilience and fragility of social housing systems in these countries. These are:

- social housing financing arrangements
- arrangements for procuring and paying for land for social housing and land use planning arrangements
- the legal status, organisation, and governance of social housing landlords, and
- the socio-economic profile of social housing tenants and the related issue of the nature and focus of tenant politics and campaigns

For reasons of space, however, the paper focuses primarily on the first two of these themes. The conclusions to the paper reflect on the implications of the analysis for the social housing literature.

2. Concepts and cases

2.1 Focus, aims and definition of terms

The terms resilience and fragility have a variety of meanings in the social scientific literature (Jacobs & Malpas, 2018). However, in this paper these terms are used in a specific and rather narrow way to refer to:

- The tendency of social housing sectors to expand (in resilient cases) or contract (which indicates fragility) over the long run in terms of the proportion of all households accommodated and,
- The ability or inability of these sectors to continue to expand or at least retain their share of households accommodated in context of challenges related to the wider political economy (e.g. economic, fiscal or banking crises, ideological and/or political opposition). The ability to withstand adverse changes in the wider political economy context is a key feature of resilient social housing sectors, fragile sectors don’t share this characteristic.

The definition of what constitutes social housing varies significantly between countries and the size and characteristics of the sector also varies depending on the particular definition used (Granath Hansson & Lundgren, 2019). Here this term is deployed in a relatively inclusive way to mean rented housing allocated according to non-market criteria (such as need or waiting time) rather than ability to pay. Other social housing researchers limit their analysis to dwellings provided by non profit or government agencies and/or let at sub-market rents, but this approach excludes large numbers

dwellings which are defined by both governments and populations as social housing. Sometimes properties for sale (at below market value or on a shared equity basis) are categorised as social housing because they are commonly provided by social landlords, but these dwellings are no longer in the control of these organisations once sold, therefore there are excluded from the analysis set out in this paper.

2.2 Which fragile and resilient social housing systems?

The analysis presented here focuses on developments since 1980 in selected social housing sectors in Western Europe. This admittedly Eurocentric focus, which ignores the significant social housing sectors in North America, Australia, New Zealand, and several of the advanced East Asian economies, was selected for pragmatic and purposeful reasons. Pragmatically, it reflects the focus of the author's previous research, publications and therefore expertise on comparative housing policy. In addition, most countries in Western Europe have social rented housing sectors which fit within the definition of social housing set out above.

For logistical reasons it was not possible to examine all Western European countries, so only six cases are examined here. Austria, Denmark, England, France, Ireland and the Netherlands were selected as case studies for examination primarily because the varying patterns of resilience and fragility evident in their social housing sectors in recent decades means that they are particularly useful for exploring this paper's central focus (see Table 1). Austria and the Netherlands are defined as having high levels of social housing in Scanlon, Whitehead & Arrigoitia (2014) comparative analysis of social housing in Europe—this tenure accommodated 23.6 and 34.1 per cent of households in these countries respectively in 2020. While Denmark and France have medium-sized social housing sectors (21.4 per cent of Danish households and 14.0 per cent of French households were social renters in 2020 and 2018 respectively). Social renting has expanded significantly in both Austria and Denmark since 1980—by 7.6 per cent in the former and 7.4 per cent in the latter, therefore both fall within the definition of resilient proposed above. Concurrently the sector grew marginally in France and remained static in the Netherlands which suggests that these sectors are resilient too but somewhat less so than their Austrian and Danish counterparts. Furthermore, the Dutch social housing sector has contracted over the longer term – it accommodated 41.1 per cent of households in 1979—so, in long term perspective, this sector appears more fragile (Elsinga & Wassenberg, 2014). Ireland's social housing sector is small—it accommodated 12.7 per cent of households in 2020 compared to 12 per cent in 1980, but contracted during some of the intervening period. Therefore this country is categorised as a fragile case in this analysis. Responsibility for housing policy was fully devolved to the governments of the countries which make up the United Kingdom in 1999 and since then significant differences have emerged between the social housing sectors of these countries (Stephens, 2019). Therefore only the English social housing sector is examined in this paper. This sector is medium-sized compared to the rest of North Western Europe (it accommodated 16.5 per cent of households in 2020) but is the most fragile of the cases examined here because it has contracted by almost half since 1980.

Table 1. Social Housing as a % of all occupied dwellings in the European Union, 1980-2020

	1980	1990	2000	Mid/late 2000s	2015	2020
Austria	16	22	23	23 ²	26.2	23.6 ⁹
Belgium	Nav	Nav	7	7 ³	Nav	4.2 ¹⁰
Bulgaria	Nav	Nav	Nav	Nav	Nav	Nav
Cyprus	Nav	0	Nav	0 ⁴	Nav	Nav
Czech Republic	Nav	40 ¹	Nav	20 ⁴	0.5	Nav
Denmark	14	17	19	19 ²	22.2	21.4
Estonia	Nav	Nav	Nav	1 ⁴	1.4	1.1 ¹²
Finland	Nav	Nav	16	16 ³	12.8	10.5 ¹²
France	15	17	17	15 ⁵	18.7	Nav
Germany	Nav	Nav	6	5 ³	3.9	2.7 ⁹
Former East Germany	Nav	74 ¹	-	-	-	-
Greece	0	0	0	0 ³	Nav	Nav
Hungary	Nav	26 ¹	Nav	3 ³	4.0	2.6 ¹⁰
Ireland	12	10	8	8 ⁴	8.7	12.7 ¹¹
Italy	5	6	5	4 ³	Nav	Nav
Latvia	Nav	74 ¹	Nav	0	0.2	1.9 ¹¹
Lithuania	Nav	Nav	Nav	Nav	Nav	0.8
Luxembourg	Nav	Nav	Nav	Nav	1.6	Nav
Malta	Nav	Nav	Nav	6 ⁴	5.5	Nav
Netherlands	34	38	34	32 ³	34.1	34.4
Poland	Nav	Nav	Nav	12	8.3	7.6 ¹¹
Portugal	Nav	Nav	Nav	Nav	2	Nav
Romania	Nav	Nav	Nav	Nav	Nav	Nav
Slovakia	Nav	27 ¹	4	4 ⁴	1.6	Nav
Slovenia	Nav	Nav	Nav	6 ⁴	6.4	4.7 ¹⁰
Spain	Nav	2	Nav	Nav	Nav	1.1 ⁹
Sweden	20	22	18	17 ³	Nav	Nav
United Kingdom	31	25	20	20 ⁴	17.6	16.7 ⁹
England	31.7 ⁷	23.0 ⁸	19.5	18.6 ⁴	17.1	16.5

Note: 1= all rented housing is categorised as social housing, on the grounds that it was mostly state owned in 1990 and although this the two sectors are not entirely equivalent, they share many key characteristics in common 2 = 2009 data. 3 = 2008 data. 4= 2004 data. 5 = 2006 data. 6 = 2007 data. 7= 1981 data. 8= 1991 data. 9 = 2019 data. 10= 2018 data. 11= 2016 data. 12= 2017 data.

Source: (Norris and Shieds, 2004; Dol and Haffner, 2010); (Ministry of Housing Communities and Local Government, no date) and (OECD, 2022). The information from all of these sources is derived from census or register data.

The particular internal features of these social housing systems which this analysis suggests have contributed to these patterns of resilience and fragility have been flagged in the introduction to the paper. Their operation in the six case study countries is outlined in Table 2 which that marked inter-country variations in this regard. In terms of the characteristics of its social housing sector, Ireland stands out as an extreme case. Its small and highly residualised social housing sector is mainly delivered by local government and almost entirely government funded (see Table 2). Local government historically also played the dominant role in the provision of social housing in England, but this is no longer the case.

Table 2. Contributors to resilient and fragile social housing systems in case study countries

Explanatory variables		Case study countries					
Theme	Details	Austria	England	Denmark	France	Ireland	Netherlands
Land for social housing	Procured at full market value?	Rarely	Sometimes	Mainly	Rarely	Almost always	Rarely until recent decades, more often in recent decades
	Procurement methods most commonly used	Public land banking	Inclusionary zoning.	Public land banking.	Inclusionary zoning.	Purchase on open market using public loans. Inclusionary zoning.	Public land banking. Inclusionary zoning
Social Housing Finance	Main source of capital funding	Private mortgage banks	Private bank loans and bonds (for housing associations). Government loans (local authorities)	Private mortgage banks	Non-market loans funded by tax free savings.	Government grants for construction, purchase and upgrading of dwellings	Private banks.
	Main source of revenue funding	Rents which reflect the cost of housing provision	Rents linked to the dwelling value and quality or to market rents (for designated new tenancies)	Rents which reflect the cost of housing provision	Rents linked to the building and financing costs.	Rents reflect tenants' incomes and generate minimal revenue.	Rents linked to housing quality (except for new dwellings).
	Number of sources of housing finance	Multiple: rents, government, bank loans and social landlords' equity.	Multiple: rents, government grants, bank loans and bonds	Multiple: rents, government, private loans, and social landlords' equity.	Multiple: rents, government, off market loans, landlords' equity.	One (almost entirely government funded)	Multiple: rents, bank loans, landlords' equity. No public supply side subsidies
	Social housing privatisation	Very limited	Extensive and highly subsidised	Very limited	None	Extensive and highly subsidised	Low pre 1990s, but high since then and subsidised.
Social Housing Landlords	Main providers of social housing	Limited profit housing associations	Non-profit housing associations (58.8%) and local authorities (41.2%)	Non-profit housing associations	Municipal housing companies and non-profit housing associations.	Local authorities (80%) and non-profit housing associations (20%).	Non-profit housing associations

Tenants	Allocation criteria	Targeted at employees/ the working class.	Targeted at the most vulnerable	Universalistic (i.e., open to most or all households).	Targeted at employees/ the working class.	Targeted at the most vulnerable	Universalistic
	Income characteristics of tenants	Middle income in housing association provided dwellings. But tenants of local authority provided social housing tend to have lower incomes.	Disadvantaged. 45% of social renting households had incomes in the lowest quintile and 37% were employed compared to 59% in all households in 2016.	Marginally below average. Average social housing tenants' household income is 68% of national average.	Average tenant household income is 74% of national average.	Disadvantaged. 35.9% of social renters had incomes below 60% of equivalised mean income in 2013, compared to 15% of homeowners.	Lower than average and falling but still contains significant mix of incomes.

Source: Carnegie, Byrne and Norris (2017); Czischke (2006); Lawson and Ruonavaara (2020) Tunstall and Pleace (2018), Scanlon, Whitehead and Arrigoitia (2014); Whitehead (2014); Wilson, (2019).

Instead non-profit sector housing associations now dominate new provision (Malpass, 2005). Housing associations are also the main social housing providers of social housing in Austria, Denmark and the Netherlands and are significant providers in France too (as are municipal housing companies which are separate from but, controlled by, local government). In Austria, Denmark, France, the Netherlands and the UK, a wide variety of sources of capital funding are used to fund the provision of new social housing, including: government grants and loans, commercial and non profit loans and tenants' and social landlords' own equity contributions (Whitehead, 2014). Table 2 also demonstrates that mechanisms employed to procure land for social housing and the extent to which land is procured at open market value or at sub market prices varies between the case study countries. In Ireland and Denmark land is mainly procured at full market prices, whereas in the other case study countries this is rarely the case.

3. Micro political economy drivers of social housing fragility and resilience

3.1 Finance

Financing arrangements exert a stronger influence on the resilience and fragility of the social housing sector compared to other pillars of the welfare state. This is because housing provision requires lumpy, up front capital spending before the service can be provided, consequently the sources, form and cost of this funding are key determinants of this tenure's strength or weakness (Ryan-Collins, Loyd & Macfarlane, 2017).

As well as being significant for the trajectories of social housing sectors, financing systems are also complex and varied between countries. This is illustrated by Table 3 which outlines the difference sources of capital funding used to build or buy new social housing or land for its development in the six case study countries. Notably, despite the level and complexity of information it presents, Table 3 does not paint a complete picture of these financing systems. It just captures funding that is monetised and therefore measurable, but non monetised mechanisms are widely used to help finance social housing in these countries. The latter includes government guarantees of borrowing, guarantee funds and transfer of cheap land and of dwellings at cost or below price by private developers (Whitehead, 2014).

Analysis of social housing systems in the six case study countries under examination indicates that three features of their capital financing arrangements have a particularly strong influence on their resilience and fragility. The first of these is the breadth of these arrangements – meaning the number and variety of sources used to fund the social housing sector and the relationship between them. Table 3 reveals marked variation between the six case study countries in this regard. Sources of capital finance vary from a single source in Ireland, whereas English and Dutch social housing providers both draw on three sources of finance, and their counterparts in Austria, Denmark and France draw on at least five. Thus, financial circuits are narrower in the countries identified as fragile in the preceding section (England, Ireland and the Netherlands) and broader in the resilient cases (Austria, Denmark and France).

Table 3. Sources of Capital Funding for New Social Housing Provision in the Case Study Countries

% of capital funding	Austria (Limited Profit Housing Associations)	Denmark	England (Housing Associations))	France	Ireland (council housing)	Netherlands
0-10	Tenants' security deposits (0-10%)	Loans from mortgage banks (86-90%)	Public capital grants (0-30%)	loans from the Caisse des Dépôts et Consignations (70%)	Central government capital grants (70-100%)	Bank loans (70-80%)
11-20	Loan from the Lander (30-40%)		Cross subsidies from cheap land or provision of market price housing for sale or rent (0-30%)			
21-30						
31-40						
41-50	LPHA's own equity (10-20%)		Bond issues and private bank loans (30-70%)	Social landlords' own equity (12-17%)	Local authority capital funds (0-30%)	
51-60						
61-70	Private bank mortgage (40-60%)		Local government loans (8-12%)	12-18% local or regional government subsidies	Social Landlords' own equity (20-30%)	
71-80						
81-90						
91-100						
Minor and/or irregular contributors		tenants' security deposits (2%). Interest rate subsidies (funded by government and the National Building Fund). Government grants of up to 5% for costs which reflect public policy priorities such as energy efficiency.		1% employer tax which part funds the government subsidies. Reduced VAT on new housing, exemption from business taxes and land purchase tax	Local property taxes (in recent years only)	

Note: Capital funding in Austria is provided within specified ranges which vary according to the project and regionally between the lander in this federal state. Capital funding in France varies according to the incomes of the tenants who qualify for the accommodation. The summary set out above VAT means Value Added Tax i.e. sales tax. Source: CECODHAS (2013) Gilmour, Washer and Lawson, (2012); Whitehead (2014); Norris and Byrne, (2017, 2018), Watt and Hodkinson, (2023).

One obvious explanation for this correspondence between the breath of financing circuits and the resilience of social housing sectors is that the combination of multiple sources of finance is more likely to result in greater funding availability and vice versa. This is clearly the case in Ireland, where the social housing sector's almost complete reliance on central government funding has severely limited levels of capital investment, particularly during periods of austerity, such as the mid-1980s and the years after the Global Financial Crisis, when government capital funding for the social house building in Ireland was radically reduced and housing output contracted radically as a result (Dukelow, 2014; Byrne & Norris, 2018). Similarly, availability of the bank lending, which provided the main source of capital funding for housing associations in England in the 1990s and early-2000s, declined significantly during the Global Financial Crisis and it took several years until alternative sources of debt from capital markets could be sourced (Williams & Whitehead, 2015). In contrast, the broad financial circuits used to fund social housing provision in Austria, Denmark and France are more likely to provide stable and adequate volumes of finance because the large number and variety of public, private and non-profit sector sources of finance reduce the likelihood that the availability of finance will be undermined by a crisis or scarcity in single funding source (Norris & Byrne, 2017).

Stability in terms of the volume and cost of capital finance provided over the medium to long term is a second feature of social housing financing arrangements that exerts a strong influence over the fragility and resilience of this tenure. Stability in the volume of capital finance is significant in this regard because fragile social housing sectors are characterised by sharp peaks and troughs in its availability (e.g. Ireland) and declining availability over the long term (e.g. England and the Netherlands) whereas more resilient social housing sectors, such as the Austrian and Danish systems, are characterised by more stable availability of finance and therefore of housing output. Byrne & Norris (2018) argue that Ireland's highly unstable and also pro-cyclical (in economic and fiscal terms) pattern of social housing funding and output also results in critical supply inefficiencies because social housing output increases in line with fiscal expansion and economic growth, construction resources and land for social housing are procured at the top of the market when value for money is poor. Furthermore, social landlords often face challenges in reviving output following periods of cuts, because they may have laid off housing development staff, for instance, or not replenished land banks or secured planning permissions (Lewis, 2019; Norris & Hayden, 2020).

As mentioned above, stability in the volume of social housing capital finance is related to the breath of financial circuits. However, this is not the only reason for the stability of capital funding in Austria, Denmark and France. In these countries social housing financing arrangements are explicitly designed to provide sufficient and stable capital funding for the sector (Norris & Byrne, 2017). In Austria, for instance, the allocation of government capital subsidies for social house building is decided on the basis of four-year agreements between central and regional government. These planning cycles associated are considered to be key to the stability of social housing output and also help ensure that public capital funding is allocated to the regions that need it most (Amann & Mundt, 2005).

In addition to stable availability of capital for housing, stability in its cost is also an important enabler of resilient social housing system. Fluctuating cost of capital make it very difficult for social landlords to plan housing development programmes and, if the costs of funds rise sharply, landlords may decide that the risks of initiating development are too high (Oxley, 2009). The capital financing arrangements employed in the Austrian, Danish and French social housing sectors are strongly focused on keeping funding costs stable, low and predictable over the long term. Four primary explicit mechanisms are used for this purpose (see Table 3). First, in Denmark interest rate subsidies (co-funded by government and the Danish National Housing fund) ensure that costs of

loans from mortgage banks remain predictable. Second, in Austria 30 per cent of development costs are covered by regional government loans, which have a fixed interest rate, set at 1 per cent at the time of writing. Third, although non-government sources provide the most of capital funding for social housing development in Austria, Denmark and France, in each case this finance is sourced from markets that are highly regulated by government to ensure that costs are low and predictable. Thus the interest rates charged by commercial banks in Austria, the government subsidised savings scheme (the Caisse des Dépôts et Consignations) which finances social housing development loans in and the yields that mortgage banks in Denmark can obtain from lending to social housing providers are all regulated by government (Norris & Byrne, 2018; Pittini, Turnbull & Yordanova, 2021). In addition, the use of equity finance, in the form of government grants (in France) and social landlords' and tenants' equity contributions (in Denmark and Austria) also insulates the sector from the risk of interest rate fluctuations on debt (Amann, Lawson & Mundt, 2009; Norris & Byrne, 2018). In contrast, housing associations in England source most of their housing capital from commercial bank loans or raise it directly on capital markets, consequently they are more directly exposed to fluctuating financial market interest rates, fees and other lender requirements (Oxley, 2009; Wainwright & Manville, 2016).

The third characteristic of arrangements for capital funding of social housing provision which is significant from the perspective of the discussion at hand is their 'permeability' – ie. the extent to which investment in social housing provision is retained within the relevant financing circuit or it seeps out. This feature is significant because, if the value generated from investment in the sector the form of rents, assets, debt repayment/ equity and most importantly surpluses (i.e. excess of revenue over costs) can be retained in the system and recycled to fund the provision of new housing or the renovation of existing dwellings to ensure they remain occupied; this contributes to the resilience of the sector Conversely, if social housing financing circuits are permeable and the value of this investment seeps out and is captured by external actors- in the form of profits, rents, assets, equity, levies, interest payments or dividends for instance - this means that the tenure will require further investment to maintain or increase its share of the housing stock. Thus, permeable circuits of finance are associated with fragile social housing systems and sealed circuits are associated with resilience (Norris & Byrne, 2017).

In contrast the Austrian, Danish and French social housing sectors employ sealed circuits of finance whereby loans (supplemented by public subsidies) are raised to fund housing development, these debts are serviced using rents and, when they have been repaid in full, rents continue to be paid and generate a surplus which funds new development. Thus, these systems are essentially 'revolving funds' although the details of their design and operation varies between countries (OECD, 2021). Denmark has a distinctive centralised mechanism for pooling the social housing surpluses and redistributing them among social landlords via its National Building Fund. Whereas in Austria revolving funds operate at individual social landlord level. Here Limited Profit Housing Associations which are required by law to reinvest surpluses in new output and receive government subsidies (of up to 3.5 per cent) for doing so (Amann, Lawson & Mundt, 2009; Pittini, Turnbull & Yordanova, 2021). Relatively low rates of sales of dwellings to tenants at below replacement price also help to minimise leakage of surpluses from the social housing sectors in all three countries and facilitate their reinvestment, as do thresholds on interest rates and/or fees that banks and other non-governmental providers of debt finance can charge for social housing development loans.

By enabling the recycling of surpluses and their reinvestment in social housing provision, these sealed financing circuits reinforce the resilience of this tenure in several important respects. First, they enable social landlords to build up equity to contribute to the costs of social housing development, thereby increasing the stability, breath and the diversity of financing circuits. Second,

they introduce a strong element of internal or self-financing into these circuits. The Austrian, Danish and French social housing sectors are not entirely self-financing because a proportion of tenants receive housing allowances in all cases but, over the very long term, they are in large part self-financing in terms of the cost of capital for new housing provision. Oxley (2009) points out that the a “high level of internal funding implies a large degree of independence for the [social] housing provider”, this insulates it from fluctuations in the availability of government and market finance and thereby reinforces its financial resilience. A third, related benefit of these self-financing arrangements, is that these mitigate the risks of political opposition to the tenure. They do this by reducing the potential for political opposition because largely self-financed social housing sector are less likely to have to compete with other pillars of the welfare state for scarce public resources and reducing its potential practical impact because by reducing reliance on public subsidies, which could be the target of retrenchment by political opponents of social housing.

The most obvious and significant fracture in social housing financing circuits through which investment can leak is via privatisation of dwellings. This has a particularly negative impact on the sector’s resilience if dwellings are sold at below replacement value and/or if there are restrictions on the reinvestment of the capital generated from sales into provision of replacement dwellings. While privatisation of social housing, via sales to tenants is permitted in all the case study countries, but the length of time for which sales have been permitted, the rate of sales and the level of the discount applied to sale prices are generally significantly higher in the fragile cases and lower in resilient social housing systems. Sales have been particularly low in Denmark; they are higher in France and Austria but remain well below the norm in the fragile social housing systems under examination here. Furthermore, in Austria dwellings are sold at market value which is likely to reflect the replacement cost (Turnbull, 2020). In contrast, sales of social housing, have been widespread in Ireland since the 1930s and (Norris, 2016) estimates that some two thirds of the total social housing stock built by local authorities in this country have been sold to tenants (see also: (O’Connell, 2007). Similarly, sales of council housing to tenants at a discount following the introduction the ‘right to buy’ in 1981 is the primary reason the English social housing sector has contracted by almost half since then (Malpass, 1990; Forrest & Murie, 2010). Crucially, successive UK governments have also placed limits on the proportion of sale proceeds which can be reinvested in in new social housing provision (Forrest & Murie, 2010).

Although the proceeding discussion has focused on the impact which arrangements for capital funding of social housing provision have on the fragility and resilience of social housing systems, it is important to note that revenue funding arrangements are also significant in this regard. In most countries rents provide the main source of revenue funding and functions in revenue flow from rents not only create difficulties for meeting local landlords’ existing management and maintenance and debt service obligations but also for securing further debt capital to develop additional housing. Thus, for revenue surety reasons, Oxley (2009) argues that setting rents at cost recovery levels (often called ‘cost rents’) has important benefits over other rent determination systems. In his view it is “better to make the link with ability to pay through housing allowances rather than using income-based rents. If it is dependent only on incomes, that revenue flow is less certain than when rents are underwritten by a housing allowance system” (Oxley, 2009). Notably, Austria, Denmark and France all employ cost rent setting arrangements, while in the three more fragile social housing sectors (Ireland, England and the Netherlands) rent is linked to income or another metric such as dwelling quality or local market rents rather than cost (see Table 3).

The cost rents paid by social housing tenants in Austria, Denmark and France play a key role in enabling stable supply and cost of capital finance for new social housing development by assuring lenders of the sector’s debt servicing capacity and low risk of default which helps to reduce interest

rates (Oxley, 2009; Pittini, Turnbull & Yordanova, 2021). In contrast the rents paid by social housing tenants in Ireland are linked progressively to incomes (higher income tenants pay higher rents and vice versa). However, in the context of a very strongly targeted social housing sector, rents generate very modest revenue which is insufficient to support access to capital by enabling debt servicing. Although, social housing rents in England do contribute to debt servicing costs (but do not cover this entirely) recent changes to rent setting that were imposed by government to reduce public spending on the housing allowances paid to tenants who can't afford their rents have reinforced the fragility of the sector. Housing associations in England were forced to cut rents by 1 per cent per annum for four years from 2016 (Wilson, 2019). This undermined the sector's creditworthiness among banks and capital market lenders and therefore their ability to borrow for long terms and at low interest rates to provide additional housing (Wilson & Barton, 2022). Cuts to housing benefit and to social security benefits more broadly introduced since 2010 have further undermined the sector's creditworthiness by reducing tenants' ability to pay and therefore the reliability of the rental income stream (Goulding, 2018 ; Beatty & Fothergill, 2014; Power et al., 2014).

3.2 Organisations

Notably, the arguments presented above about the importance of diverse sources of finance, including commercial and non-profit finance, in supporting the resilience of social housing systems support the enormously influential thesis proffered in Kemeny's (1995) landmark book on systems of rented housing provision—From Public Housing to the Social Market. Here Kemeny posits that independence from government, including financial independence but also organisational independence (which is achieved by having non-governmental organisations provide social housing) is associated with larger and more resilient social housing sectors. Conversely, he argues that direct government provision of social housing and reliance on the exchequer to fund this sector is associated with small and residualised social housing sectors. Among the six cases under examination Ireland, which is one of the least resilient, is the only one where most social housing is provided directly by municipalities. Although this was also the case until the late 1980s in England.

3.3 Tenants

Tenants' ability to pay cost rents, which support the financial resilience of the social housing sector, is strongly related to the socio-economic profile for the tenant population. If social housing is strongly focussed on very low-income tenants, the ability of the tenant body to pay cost rents is obviously limited and they require an either a significant subsidy from government or rents that don't reflect cost but are related to incomes or some other measure of affordability. As explained above, this would be expected to constrain new housing output and thereby the size of the social housing sector. Whereas, in less progressively targeted systems tenants can afford to make a more substantial contribution to funding costs or fund the service in its entirety which suggests that constraints on output are weaker.

However, the significance of targeting for social housing resilience and fragility is not only financial but also political, because larger and less residualised social housing sectors are less likely to be marginalised from mainstream political concerns. Malpass and Victory (2010) argue that this has happened in the UK since its social housing sector has contracted and become increasingly targeted on the poorest (Bradley, 2014). As the ethnic minority population has become more concentrated in social housing across many Western European countries, the political marginalization of this sector has also become more racialised (Arbaci, 2007). Conversely, although there are examples of resistance against the residualisation of social housing by tenants across Western Europe (McCormack, 2009; Hodkinson, 2011), higher income tenants are more likely to

have the resources and political influence to campaign successfully to protect and expand their tenure. This is evident in Denmark where tenants play a central role and have a say in social housing management decisions, which has helped to maintain the size of the sector and opposing politicians' privatisation efforts in recent years (Cole & Etherington, 2005; Lennartz, 2011).

3.4 Land

Social housing is distinctive amongst the core elements of the welfare state as far as access to land is vital for its supply and the costs of this land must generally be paid for in full before the dwellings are provided. However, particularly in cities, where affordability challenges and therefore social housing need is most acute, sites for housing are in short supply and are expensive and have become more so in recent decades due to the impact of financialisation on land markets and also due to land use planning which has constrained land development opportunities. In some cases, such as Hong Kong, the provision of free land by government has enabled the social housing sector to expand rapidly (Chui, 2013). Whereas in many other countries social landlords must compete against speculative private investors and developers for sites which significantly increases their costs and therefore the challenges associated with supplying the new social housing (Ryan-Collins, Loyd & Macfarlane, 2017). Therefore, the willingness of government to engage in 'active management' of the supply and cost of land for social housing is a key influence on the resilience and fragility of social housing systems.

With this in mind, there has been a clear and visible change in the arrangements for procuring land for social housing and reducing the cost of this land in several of the case study countries since World War II. The enormous expansion of the English and Dutch social housing sectors in the post-war period was underpinned by measures to actively manage the supply and reduce the cost of land for social housing that were very radical by contemporary standards. English municipalities enjoyed the power to compulsorily purchase land at existing use value during the post-War period and in the Netherlands municipalities' procured servicing of almost all raw development land and thereby were the main source of land for all housing tenures, not just social housing (Cox, 1984; Needham, Koenders & Kruijt, 1993; Needham, 1997). These mechanisms helped to decommodify land markets in both countries, which reduced the prices paid for land for social housing and thereby provided an enormous invisible subsidy to this sector that reduced the subsidy it required from government to provide new housing. However, English municipalities compulsory purchase powers were dismantled from the 1960s contributed to declining social house building from the 1960s. Active management of land arrangements remained in place in the Netherlands for much longer and enabled much higher levels of social housing output in this country until recent decades. However, the rolling back of these measures since the 1990s has made an important contribution to the contraction of Dutch social housing sector by significantly increasing the price and restricting the supply of land for social house building (Buitelaar, 2010).

Among the three countries categorised as resilient in recent decades, only Denmark has consistently employed active land management measures since World War II. It introduced a land tax in the early twentieth century which has remained in place since then. While not specifically intended to directly support the management of land supply for social housing this land tax provides important indirect support for the tenure, by improving the functioning of the land use planning system and increasing the costs of land hoarding when land prices are high and thereby encouraging counter-cyclical land supply. Active land management measures were introduced in France in the mid-1950s but only began to effectively operate a decade later, while this policy emerged in Austria during the 1980s (Pearsall, 2021). In both countries this policy has been

consistently reformed, updated, and expanded since its introduction and has played an important role in enabling the expansion of the social housing sector in recent decades.

The chronological review of active management of land for social housing outlined above also suggest that the importance of active land management policies to the resilience of this tenure has increased in recent decades. During the post-war decades, commercial house building sector was non-operational or weak, which reduced competition for land and land prices. Thus, in Ireland and Austria municipalities managed to accumulate substantial land banks for social house building during this period in the absence of any active land management policies. Since the late 1960s and 1970s however, residential land to restrictions on land uses related to the expansion of land use planning systems and increased flows of investment into land and property related to financialisation among other factors have contributed to marked increases in development land prices, particularly in high-growth Western European cities (Buitelaar & de Kam, 2012; Watling & Breach, 2023b). Thus, as the land market context in which social housing landlords operate has become more challenging, active management of land has become even more vital for sourcing affordable land for social housing building.

4. Conclusions

The long term trajectories of social rented housing systems, in terms of the proportion of households they accommodate, are undoubtedly shaped by the macro political context in which they operate. However, this paper has argued that social housing systems also have an 'internal' economy, politics and social profile and this 'micro-political economy' also influences their fragility and resilience.

My presentation today has presented analysis of the implications of this for the dominant analyses for the research literature on social housing. However, the ideas presented here can also inform the design of policies and campaigns to protect and expand social housing.

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